

МАКРОЕКОНОМІЧНІ АСПЕКТИ СУЧАСНОЇ ЕКОНОМІКИ

UDC 336

RUSINA Yu. O.

The budget process in Ukraine in the context of martial law: features and prospects

The subject of the research is the theoretical and practical basis for researching the features and prospects of the budget process in Ukraine under martial law.

The aim of the research is to identify the main elements of the budget process under martial law in Ukraine and to propose promising areas of the budget process after the end of martial law.

Research methods. The study used general economic and specific methods: tabular and graphical method, method of comparison and analysis, statistical method, analysis of the political context, socio-economic analysis.

Results of the investigation. It is determined that the budget process is a key element of the State's financial policy, which determines the mechanism of formation, distribution and use of public financial resources. It is proved that under martial law, this process is of particular importance, since it requires a rapid response to changes in external and internal threats and challenges related to the need to maintain the country's defense capability, ensure the stability of the socio-economic situation, and implement humanitarian programs. It is established that in Ukraine, under martial law, the budgetary process has undergone significant changes due to the need for a prompt response to military operations, special defense programs and the preservation of economic stability. It is found that the main feature of the budget process during martial law is the need to adapt to rapidly changing circumstances, since the budget is formed under conditions of uncertainty about the duration of hostilities, which makes it difficult to forecast revenues and expenditures. The author proposes to improve the budget process under martial law by introducing comprehensive measures that will help to increase the efficiency of public finance use and ensure economic stability.

Scope of the results. Budget management, Finance, Local finance, Budgeting, National economy.

Conclusions. The budget process in Ukraine under martial law is extremely important for ensuring the country's defense capability and maintaining its social and economic stability. Despite a number of problems and challenges, Ukraine continues to actively adapt the budget process to the new conditions, in particular by increasing transparency, resource efficiency and mobilizing internal and external reserves. In the future, after the end of hostilities, the government will face the need to implement comprehensive reforms to restore the economy and reduce the debt burden. A stable budget process

in the post-war recovery will be a key factor in ensuring economic growth and improving the welfare of the Ukrainian population.

Keywords: budget process, martial law, socio-economic stability, reforms, expenditures and revenues, debt burden, public finance, economic policy.

РУСІНА Ю. О.

Бюджетний процес в Україні в контексті воєнного стану: особливості та перспективи

Предметом дослідження є теоретичні та практичні основи дослідження особливостей та перспектив бюджетного процесу в Україні в умовах воєнного стану.

Метою дослідження є визначення основних елементів бюджетного процесу в умовах воєнного стану в Україні та запропонування перспективних напрямів бюджетного процесу після завершення воєнного стану.

Методи дослідження. При дослідженні було використано загальноекономічні та специфічні методи: таблично-графічний метод, метод порівняння та аналізу, статистичний метод, аналіз політичного контексту, соціально-економічного аналізу.

Результати роботи. Визначено, що бюджетний процес є ключовим елементом фінансової політики держави, який визначає механізм формування, розподілу та використання державних фінансових ресурсів. Доведено, що в умовах воєнного стану цей процес набуває особливої ваги, оскільки потребує швидкого реагування на зміну зовнішніх і внутрішніх загроз та викликів, пов'язаних з необхідністю підтримки обороноздатності країни, забезпечення стабільності соціально-економічної ситуації, а також реалізації гуманітарних програм. Встановлено, що в Україні в умовах воєнного стану бюджетний процес зазнав значних змін, які пов'язані з необхідністю оперативного реагування на військові дії, проведення спеціальних програм оборонного характеру та збереження економічної стабільності. З'ясовано, що основною особливістю бюджетного процесу під час воєнного стану є необхідність адаптації до швидко змінюваних обставин, оскільки бюджет формується в умовах невизначеності щодо тривалості воєнних дій, що ускладнює прогнозування доходів і видатків. Запропоновано вдосконалення бюджетного процесу в умовах воєнного стану через впровадження комплексних заходів, що сприятимуть підвищенню ефективності використання державних фінансів та забезпеченню економічної стабільності.

Галузь застосування результатів. Бюджетний менеджмент, фінанси, місцеві фінанси, бюджетування, національна економіка.

Висновки. Бюджетний процес в Україні в умовах воєнного стану є надзвичайно важливим для забезпечення обороноздатності країни та підтримки її соціально-економічної стабільності. Незважаючи на низку проблем та викликів, Україна продовжує активно адаптувати бюджетний процес до нових умов, зокрема через підвищення прозорості, ефективності використання ресурсів та мобілізацію внутрішніх і зовнішніх резервів. У майбутньому після завершення військових дій уряд зіткнеться з необхідністю реалізації комплексних реформ для відновлення економіки та зменшення боргового навантаження. Стабільний бюджетний процес в умовах післявоєнного відновлення стане ключовим чинником для забезпечення економічного зростання та підвищення добробуту населення України.

Ключові слова: бюджетний процес, воєнний стан, соціально-економічна стабільність, реформи, видатки і доходи, боргове навантаження, державні фінанси, економічна політика.

Formulation of the problem. The budget process is a key element of public administration that ensures the functioning of the economy and social sphere. In the context of martial law, which was introduced in Ukraine after the beginning of Russia's full-scale invasion in 2022, the budget process has undergone significant changes and challenges.

The budget process is a key element of the state's financial policy, which determines the mechanism for the formation, distribution and use of public financial resources. In the context of martial law, this process is of particular importance, as it requires a rapid response to changes in external and internal threats and challenges related to the need to

maintain the country’s defense capability, ensure the stability of the socio–economic situation, and implement humanitarian programs [1; 3; 5].

In Ukraine, under martial law, the budget process has undergone significant changes due to the need to respond quickly to military operations, conduct special defense programs, and maintain economic stability [2; 4; 8].

Analysis of research and publications on the problem. The budget process has always been of interest to the scientific community, especially the issues of the state’s financial policy, which determines the mechanism of formation, distribution and use of public financial resources. Among economists, considerable attention has been paid by the

following scholars: S. Baranov, N. Hvazava, O. Denysiuk, O. Denis, O. Dzhyhora, O. Dmytryk, Yu. Kohut, V. Malyshko, L. Yaremenko, O. Kalmykov, O. Panukhnyk, Ya. Fedotova, N. Holych, Yu. Petlenko, N. Drozd, D. Morhun, N. Prots, N. Demchuk, M. Riabokin, O. Hordei, O. Novytska, Ye. Kotukh, N. Kozii, K. Tokarieva and others [1–15]. However, the issues of the budget process during the war are not fully considered, which makes the study quite relevant.

Presenting main material. The budget process is a systematized activity of public authorities to develop, approve, execute and monitor the state budget. Under normal conditions, this process is cyclical and structured, which helps to ensure the stability of economic policy. However, in crisis situ–

Table 1. Main stages of the budget process under martial law

№	Stage	Characteristics.
1	Budget planning	During the period of martial law, budget planning needs to be adjusted to take into account the sharp increase in defense, security and social spending. The main document regulating budget planning is the Budget Code of Ukraine, but under martial law, special regulations governing the allocation of financial resources may be introduced.
2	Adoption of the budget	Under martial law, this stage may be carried out under an accelerated procedure. The Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine can adopt amendments to the budget in a short time, based on the needs of the army, the defense industry and other urgent state tasks. One of the main tasks remains to ensure transparency of the budget process, given the challenges associated with limited time for decision–making.
3	Budget execution	Implementation of the budget under martial law includes, among other things, the prompt reallocation of funds within priority areas. The role of executive authorities is growing, as they must take measures to ensure funding for critical programs. The main expenditures are directed to defense, social protection, healthcare, infrastructure restoration, and refugee assistance.
4	Control over budget execution	During the martial law period, control over the efficiency of the use of budget funds is strengthened, as their distribution becomes critical to national security. Particular attention is paid to the fight against corruption and misuse of funds.
5	Reporting and audit	During martial law, reporting on budget execution takes place in difficult conditions. Reports may be limited in order to maintain information security, but the government must ensure sufficient transparency for the public and international partners, especially in the case of international financial assistance.
6	Increasing defense spending	Budget expenditures on defense and security are becoming a priority, requiring a significant reduction or temporary suspension of funding for some other government programs.
7	International assistance	Under martial law, Ukraine actively receives international financial assistance, including grants, loans, and other types of support. An important aspect is the efficient and transparent use of these funds.
8	Tax and budget policy	Military operations have led to the need to introduce changes in the tax system. Declining business revenues, falling exports, and economic instability are forcing the government to look for new sources of revenue and develop mechanisms to stimulate economic activity.
9	Social programs	A significant portion of the budget is allocated to social protection of the population, including internally displaced persons and those who lost their jobs as a result of the war. Social payments and support for low–income groups are becoming one of the key areas of budget policy.
10	Attracting internal reserves	To finance the military operations and social programs, the government has to mobilize internal reserves, including public and private funds, military loan bonds, and other financial instruments.

Source [2–6].

ations, such as martial law, the budget process can be modified to respond quickly to new challenges. This requires flexibility in public finance management, acceleration of decision-making processes, and attraction of additional resources to support critical areas such as defense, social protection, and infrastructure rehabilitation [6; 9; 10].

The budget process in Ukraine includes several stages: planning, budget adoption, budget execution, budget monitoring and reporting. Under normal circumstances, these stages are quite regulated and involve the participation of legislative and executive authorities. However, under martial law, these procedures change according to the needs of the country [7; 11; 15].

The main stages of the budget process in Ukraine are shown in Table 1.

The introduction of martial law in Ukraine was accompanied by a number of changes in the budget process, namely:

1. Allocation of budgetary resources for defense and security, where one of the key changes was a significant increase in defense and security spending, which is natural in a situation of military operations. In the state budget for 2023, expenditures for these purposes amounted to more than 40% of the total amount, which is significantly higher than pre-war figures.

2. Adaptation to reduced revenues. Due to the destruction of businesses, reduced export opportunities, and loss of territory, Ukraine faced a significant decline in budget revenues, forcing the government to resort to international aid, lending, and wartime bonds.

3. Simplification of budget procedures. The Government decided to simplify some budget procedures for faster allocation of funds, which reduced bureaucratic delays in reallocating funds between budget items and allowed for a quicker response to unforeseen circumstances.

4. Financing of critical industries. Along with defense spending, special attention is paid to financing social programs, medical care, and the restoration of damaged infrastructure. Despite the shortage of funds, the government tried to provide basic social benefits and support to vulnerable groups.

Thus, the main feature of the budget process during martial law is the need to adapt to rapidly changing circumstances, since the budget is formed in conditions of uncertainty about the duration of hostilities, which complicates the forecasting of revenues and expenditures [12; 13; 14; 15].

The main problems faced by the budget process under martial law include the following:

- uncertainty – the unstable situation at the front and economic fluctuations complicate budget planning;

Fig. 1. Main prospects of the budget process after the end of martial law in Ukraine

Source: [3–5].

- inflation – significant spending on defense and social programs may lead to inflationary pressure on the economy;

- budget deficit – increased expenditures and decreased revenues create a budget deficit problem that requires additional funds to be raised through borrowing;

Problems with the efficient use of resources – during the war, the risk of inefficient use of budget funds increases due to hasty decision-making and corruption risks.

In order to overcome these obstacles in the budget process, we can offer the following perspectives of the budget process after the end of martial law (Fig. 1).

Thus, in order to improve the budget process under martial law, it is necessary to implement comprehensive measures that will increase the efficiency of public finances and ensure economic stability:

- automation of processes – the introduction of the latest technologies to automate budget processes can increase their transparency and efficiency, as well as reduce the risks of abuse;

- improving financial literacy – developing special programs to improve the financial literacy of civil servants and business executives can contribute to a more rational allocation of resources;

- international cooperation – cooperation with international organizations in the field of public financial management will allow to use best practices to improve the budget process;

- involvement of the public in control – Ensuring greater involvement of civil society in the process of controlling the budget implementation will help to increase the level of trust in the government and the effectiveness of its decisions.

Conclusions

The budget process in Ukraine under martial law is extremely important for ensuring the country's defense capability and maintaining its social and economic stability. Despite a number of problems and challenges, Ukraine continues to actively adapt the budget process to the new conditions, in particular by increasing transparency, resource efficiency and mobilizing internal and external reserves. In the future, after the end of hostilities, the government will face the need to implement comprehensive reforms to restore the economy and reduce the debt burden. A stable budget process in the post-war recovery

will be a key factor in ensuring economic growth and improving the welfare of the Ukrainian population.

References:

1. Baranov, S. (2020). Problemni pytannia protsesu biudzhethnoi detsentralizatsii v Ukraini [Problematic issues of the process of budget decentralization in Ukraine]. *Pidpriemnytstvo, gospodarstvo i pravo = Entrepreneurship, economy and law*. – 2020. – № 3. – С. 115–120 [in Ukrainian].

2. Hvazava, N. H. (2022). Efektyvnist diialnosti derzhavnoho upravlinnia u biudzhethnomu protsesi Ukrainy [Efficiency of public administration in the budget process of Ukraine]. *Naukovyi pohliad: ekonomika ta upravlinnia. =Scientific view: economics and management*. – 2022. – № 2. – С. 97–103 [in Ukrainian].

3. Denysiuk, O. V. (2019). Otsinka efektyvnosti biudzhethnoho protsesu v Ukraini [Evaluation of the effectiveness of the budget process in Ukraine]. *Biznes Inform = Business Inform*. – 2019. – № 3. – С. 286–291 [in Ukrainian].

4. Denis, O. V. (2017). Osoblyvosti pravovoho rehulivannia biudzhethnoho protsesu v Ukraini [Features of legal regulation of the budget process in Ukraine]. *Aktualni problemy vitchyznianoï yurysprudentsii =Actual problems of domestic jurisprudence*. – 2017. – Issue 6(2). – С. 81–85 [in Ukrainian].

5. Denis, O. V. (2018). Poniattia, osoblyvosti ta pryntsyipy biudzhethnoho protsesu na mistsevomu rivni Ukrainy [Concept, features and principles of the budget process at the local level of Ukraine]. *Yevropeiski perspektyvy = European Perspectives*. – 2018. – № 3. – С. 5–10 [in Ukrainian].

6. Dzhyhora, O. M. (2022). Osoblyvosti zabezpechennia biudzhethnoho protsesu ta biudzhethnoi bezpeky Ukrainy v umovakh voiennoho stanu [Features of ensuring the budget process and budgetary security of Ukraine under martial law]. *Ekonomichniy visnyk Dniprovskoi politekhniki = Economic Bulletin of Dnipro Polytechnic*. – 2022. – № 2. – С. 136–147 [in Ukrainian].

7. Dmytryk, O. O. (2018). Biudzhethnyi protses v Ukraini v suchasnykh umovakh [The budget process in Ukraine in modern conditions]. *Pravo ta innovatsiine suspilstvo = Law and innovative society*. – 2018. – № 1. – С. 62 [in Ukrainian].

8. Kohut, Yu. M. (2019). Osoblyvosti biudzhethnoho protsesu v Ukraini [Features of the budget process in Ukraine]. *Naukovyi visnyk Uzhhorodskoho natsionalnoho universytetu = Scientific Bulletin of Uzhhorod National University. Series: International economic relations and the world economy*. – 2019. – Issue 27(1). – С. 62–66 [in Ukrainian].

9. Malyshko, V. V., Yaremenko, L. M., Kalmykov, O. V. (2023). Napriamy rozvytku biudzhethnoho protsesu v Ukraini [Directions of development of the budget process in Ukraine]. *Investytsii: praktyka ta dosvid = Investments: practice and experience.* – 2023. – № 3. – С. 33–38 [in Ukrainian].

10. Panukhnyk, O., Fedotova, Ya., Holych, N. (2023). Derzhavnyi biudzheth Ukrainy–2023: osoblyvosti rehulivannia finansovo–ekonomichnykh protsesiv v umovakh povnomasshtabnoi viiny [State Budget of Ukraine–2023: features of regulation of financial and economic processes in a full–scale war]. *Sotsialno–ekonomichni problemy i derzhava = Socio–economic problems and the state.* – 2022. – Issue 2. – P. 63–71 [in Ukrainian].

11. Petlenko, Yu. V., Drozd, N. V., Morhun, D. O. (2021). Vidkrytist ta prozorst biudzhethnoho protsesu v Ukraini [Openness and transparency of the budget process in Ukraine]. *Naukovyi visnyk Lotnoi akademii = Scientific Bulletin of the Flight Academy. Series: Economics, management and law.* – 2021. – Issue 5. – P. 83–91 [in Ukrainian].

12. Prots, N., Demchuk, N. (2022). Aktualni problemy formuvannia ta vykonannia mistsevykh biudzhethiv v umovakh voiennoho stanu [Actual problems of formation and execution of local budgets under martial law]. *Ekonomichnyi chasopys Volynskoho natsionalnoho universytetu imeni Lesi Ukrainky = Economic Journal of Lesya Ukrainka Volyn National University.* – 2022. – № 4. – С. 62–70 [in Ukrainian].

13. Puzyrova, P. V., Martsynovskyi, V. V., Svyrydov, A. O. (2023). Sutnist ta znachennia makroprudentsiinoi poli-

tyky u fokusi finansovoi stabilnosti Ukrainy [The essence and significance of macroprudential policy in the focus of financial stability of Ukraine]. *Formuvannia rynkovykh vidnosyn v Ukraini = Formation of market relations in Ukraine.* 2023 – No. 7–8 (266–267). – pp. 5–11 [in Ukrainian].

14. Riabokin, M. V., Hordei, D., Novytska, O. V., Kotukh, Ye. V., Kozii, N. S. (2022). Osoblyvosti biudzhethnoho protsesu v umovakh voiennoho stanu [Features of the budget process under martial law]. *Ekonomika i rehion = Ekonomika i region.* – 2022. – № 4. – С. 275–281 [in Ukrainian].

15. Tokarieva, K. O. Pravove rehulivannia biudzhethnoho protsesu v umovakh voiennoho stanu [Legal regulation of the budget process under martial law]. *Pravo i Bezpeka = Law and Security.* – 2022. – № 3. – С. 26–36 [in Ukrainian].

Дані про автора

Русіна Юлія Олександрівна,

доцент кафедри фінансів та бізнес–консалтингу, Київський національний університет технологій та дизайну, к.е.н., доцент

e–mail: rusinaulia80@gmail.com

Data about the author

Yuliia Rusina,

Associate Professor of the Department of Finance and Business Consulting, Kyiv National University of Technologies and Design, Ph.D. in Economics, Associate Professor

e–mail: rusinaulia80@gmail.com

UDC 330.34:339.92:338.5

PUZYROVA P. V.,
PYLYPENKO O. O.,
HONCHARUK Ye. L.

Methodological approaches to the formation and development of the economic potential of transnational corporations in conditions of turbulence and risk

The subject of the research is to determine the main methodological approaches to the formation and development of the economic potential of transnational corporations in the current conditions of turbulence and risk.

The aim of the research is to determine the methodological foundations, principles, impact of risks and turbulence on the formation and development of the economic potential of transnational corporations.

Research methods. The following methods were used in the study: theoretical analysis; economic analysis; factor analysis; scenario analysis; risk management; case study; systematic; tabular, etc.

Results of the investigation. It has been established that transnational corporations (TNCs) are central to the modern global economy and their impact on the economic development of countries is